

HISTORY OF INTERNET JOURNALISM IN KARAKALPAKSTAN

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<https://www.doi.org/10.37547/ejar-v03-i02-p3-112>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 11th February 2023

Accepted: 19th February 2023

Online: 20th February 2023

KEY WORDS

Victory news tools, sites,
internet, online newspaper.

ABSTRACT

This article says that with the advent of the Internet in Karakalpakstan, the Internet has become closer in the media, as well as the emergence of Internet journalism in Karakalpakstan. Digital journalism, also known as online journalism, is a contemporary form of journalism where editorial content is distributed via the Internet, as opposed to publishing via print or broadcast. What constitutes digital journalism is debated by scholars; however, the primary product of journalism, which is news and features on current affairs, is presented solely or in combination as text, audio, video, or some interactive forms like newsgames, and disseminated through digital media technology. The first type of digital journalism, called teletext, was invented in the UK in 1970. Teletext is a system allowing viewers to choose which stories they wish to read and see it immediately. The information provided through teletext is brief and instant, similar to the information seen in digital journalism today. [citation needed] The information was broadcast between the frames of a television signal in what was called the Vertical Blanking Interval or VB. American journalist, Hunter S. Thompson relied on early digital communication technology beginning by using a fax machine to report from the 1971 US presidential campaign trail as documented in his book Fear and Loathing on the Campaign Trail.

The production of programs that help to cover the socio-political, economic and cultural life of the country is related to the media. The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "Strategy of Action", June 27, 2019 "On additional measures to ensure the independence of the media and the development of reference services of national agencies and organizations" led to the development of Victory Media in the country. Internet journalism in Karakalpakstan began to develop after independence. At the same time, Internet journalism has also developed in Uzbekistan. In a historically short period

of time, the Internet has become a major determinant of the capabilities of modern media. The Internet has become a tool for the rapid dissemination of information, not only in our country, but also around the world, a democratic platform for analyzing social issues. The emergence of Internet journalism in Karakalpakstan can be divided into 4 stages:

1. Structure of websites of government agencies and non-government sectors.
2. Development of electronic versions of software Victory News.
3. Creating online websites.
4. Establishment of a social networking platform for websites. [1: 3-75]

The Internet first entered Uzbekistan in 1996 with the help of a Russian Internet provider. Earlier this year, government agencies began connecting to the Internet. In 1996, 3 websites were launched in Karakalpakstan. The first website of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan in the Karakalpak language, WWW.sovmnrk.gov.uz, was launched in 1997. [2:34]

On February 7, 2002, the website "Erkin Karakalpakstan" and "Vesti Karakalpakstana", organized by the Karakalpakstan Agency for Appeals and Information, created the website WWW.erkinkarakalpak.uz. This site received the first electronic printable static that produces information in the Karakalpak language. In 2006, the website WWW.qq.jaslari.uz of Karakalpakstan Yoshlar, a social and political newspaper for the youth of Karakalpakstan, was launched. [3:47]

In 2009, the website of the children's and youth newspaper "Jetkinshek" WWW.Jetkinshek.uz became one of the means of Internet victory news. An example of an Internet media is Nukus FM, which launched online in 2010.

In those years, the number of mobile Internet users in Karakalpakstan was 4,000. In 2011, the first online journalism website was launched in Karakalpakstan. Thus, the website of the Karakalpak News Agency WWW.xabar.uz appeared in 2012, and in 2014 the website WWW.makan.uz was launched. Evidence that the Internet is a new means of communication in Karakalpakstan and its peculiarities, the journalist WWW.kar24.uz used the opportunities of journalistic participation and style in covering various topics. [1: 80-120]

Conclusion

In conclusion, various measures are being taken in Karakalpakstan to develop Internet journalism. Today, everyone in society has access to the Internet. The media of victory, known as the "Fourth Estate," have played a tremendous role in the development of society. The creation of online forms or personal websites of victory media such as television, radio, newspapers creates opportunities for everyone. In the democratization of the political and economic life of the country, in the strengthening of the ideology of national independence, the media, radio and television, which serve the emergence of new public opinion, play a significant role. In 1994, journalists made their first tentative steps onto the internet. Just a few years later, online journalists were at the cutting edge of news reporting, both during and after the destruction of the World Trade Center on 11 September 2001. As that crisis unfolded, telegraph.co.uk serviced 600 page requests per second. In just one decade online journalism has become central to peoples' lives and as a result, some have abandoned print news altogether. Journalism.co.uk has created a timeline that plots the development of online news - not a comprehensive list of every success and failure, but an outline of many of the

events and debates that have shaped the craft of online journalism in the UK since 1994. BBC Online starts as a full service. In less than one year it offers more than 140,000 pages of content and 61,000 pages of news.

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